

ELECTROMAGNETIC CHARACTERIZATION OF THREE RF LEAK DETECTORS

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Abstract

Three electromagnetic leak detectors (RF Sniffers) have been evaluated as quantitative hardness surveillance tools. The leak detectors included a low frequency (150 kHz) twin loop system that measured shielding effectiveness according to the MIL-STD-285 definition, a unit that used skin current injection (SCI) and a ferrite coil sensor, and transmitter/receiver that operated in the UHF range (462 MHz). First, the electromagnetic characteristics of the leak detectors were measured. Then the performance of the leak detectors was determined in the laboratory using a set of calibrated apertures whose shielding effectiveness had been predicted using polarizability theory. Finally, the leak detectors were used to measure the shielding effectiveness of hardened and unhardened apertures on a large commercial aircraft. With some modification to the operating procedures, each of the leak detectors could be used in a semi quantitative manner.

Introduction

Electromagnetically hardened systems typically use conductive topological shielding surfaces to keep the external EM environment from reaching critical electronic circuits on the inside and vice versa. These surfaces can act as EM shields only if they do not contain significant faults or defects such as apertures, joints or conductive penetrations. To ensure that the EM performance of these shielding surfaces is adequate, tests must be performed at various times during the lifetime of the system. One of the simplest tests that can be performed is an EM leak detector test. In this type of test, a signal is applied to one side of the shielding surface using illumination or injection techniques, and the amount of EM energy that gets through the surface is measured with appropriate sensors.

EM leak detectors, or sniffers, typically operate at a single frequency and are relatively small, sensitive and convenient to use. They have been used in a qualitative way to check screen rooms and other enclosures. They are generally extremely successful in locating/identifying faults and defects in the shielding surface. They are normally less successful in quantitatively characterizing each of the faults or defects. In fact, they generally have not had a good reputation as tools for serious hardness surveillance measurements. To some extent this is due to the simple nature of the equipment. To a larger extent, it is due to a lack of understanding of how defects degrade the shielding surface and the fact that EM leak detectors tend to measure parameters such as shielding effectiveness which are not intrinsic EM parameters, even when they are used in a semi-quantitative manner.

When used with understanding, EM leak detectors should have the potential of being extremely useful quantitative tools for identifying, isolating, and

hopefully, characterizing faults or defects in EM shielding surfaces. The goal of this effort was to characterize and understand a variety of EM leak detectors so that they could be used in a quantitative manner.

Three electromagnetic leak detectors (RF Sniffers) were evaluated as hardness surveillance tools. The leak detectors included a low frequency (150 kHz) twin loop system that measured shielding effectiveness according to the MIL-STD-285 definition of shielding effectiveness, a unit that used skin current injection (SCI) and a ferrite coil sensor, and transmitter/receiver that operated in the UHF range (461 MHz). These will be referred to as LF285 (Low Frequency 285), LFSCI (Low Frequency Skin Current Injection) and UHF (Ultra High Frequency).

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Laboratory Evaluation

The laboratory evaluation of the EM leak detectors was divided into two parts. First the electromagnetic characteristics, such as operating frequency, output power, field distribution, receiver sensitivity and bandwidth were measured. Then the ability of the leak detectors to measure calibrated apertures was determined.

Electromagnetic Characterization

The LF285 leak detector consisted of two units: a transmitter and a receiver. Each unit had a large loop antenna and the associated battery operated electronics. The units could be operated with the loops coplanar or parallel. The former orientation was referred to as the MIL-STD-285 orientation and the latter was called the NSA orientation. Spacers were incorporated in the devices so that the center to center distance could be conveniently maintained at approximately 1 m. The LF285 leak detector operated at a frequency of 150 kHz. Therefore it had a wavelength of 2 km. The output of the transmitter unit was measured by measuring the effective current through the loop with a current probe and was found to be 3.26 A-turns. The magnetic field produced by the LF 285 transmitter was measured as a function of distance. The results are shown in Figure 1. The left hand ordinate is the output of the measurement antenna in dBm and the right hand ordinate gives the magnetic field in mA/m for selected values. Also shown is a line that has an inverse cube dependence such as is expected from a magnetic dipole. The measured fields are consistent with such a field dependence. The receiving antenna of the LF285 leak

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detector was a ten turn loop. The receiver bandwidth was 300 Hz. After adjusting the receiver and transmitter units according to the instructions, the receiver noise level corresponded to a shielding effectiveness of 85 dB.

Figure 1. Magnetic Field Produced by the LF285 Transmitter Unit

The UHF leak detector consisted of transmitter and receiver units operating at a frequency of 462.6 MHz. The wavelength corresponding to this frequency is 0.65 m. The transmitter and receiver units were equipped with small flexible vertical monopoles. The units themselves provided the ground plane for the monopoles. The transmitter was powered by the a.c. mains. The transmitter output had three output settings: 0.1 W, 1.0 W and 10 W. When measured with a 50 Ohm load, the output power of the transmitter was 56 mW, 0.355 W, and 2.8 W for these three settings. Figure 2 shows the electric field measured at various distances from the transmitter when the system was set up in a large high bay work area. The left hand ordinate is the output of the measurement sensor in dBm and the right hand ordinate gives the electric field in mV/m at selected points. Also shown on Figure 2 is a line that corresponds to an inverse distance relationship. The electric field produced by the transmitter appears to be consistent with this relationship for distances up to 2 m. Beyond 2 m, the field does not fall off. This may be due to reflections within the room where the measurements were made.

Figure 2. Electric Field Produced by the UHF Leak Detector Transmitter

The LFSCI leak detector consisted of two units—an a.c. powered signal generator for injecting the currents on one side of the shielding enclosure and a battery operated receiver with a ferrite coil sensor for measuring the magnetic fields on the other side of the shielding enclosure. The LFSCI leak detector operated at a frequency of 95 kHz. This corresponds to a wavelength of 3.2 km. The receiver

had a bandwidth of 2.5 kHz. The signal generator had two output power settings. The measured output power that corresponded to these settings was 0.8 and 16.2 W. The field distribution of this leak detector was characterized by connecting the units signal generator to a 4' x 8' sheet of brass and measuring the surface magnetic field using a multigap loop (MGL) sensor which had a known sensitivity. The results are shown in Figure 3. The numbers in parentheses are the coordinates in inches relative to the lower left hand corner of the plate. The surface magnetic field is given in mA/m. The current injection points were in the middle of the plate for the left hand measurements and were on opposite corners for the right hand sheet. Examination of these measurements shows that the current spreads out and is surprisingly uniform, particularly when it is injected corner to corner.

Figure 3. Surface Magnetic Field Distribution Produced by the LFSCI Detector

Quantitative Shielding Performance Measurements

The second phase of the laboratory evaluation of the electromagnetic leak detectors consisted of installing well defined circular apertures (0.5 to 4 inches in diameter) in the wall of a screen room and measuring the shielding effectiveness of this section of the screen room with each of the leak detectors. The shielding effectiveness of these apertures had previously been predicted using polarizability theory [1].

The results are shown in Figure 4. The readings of the LFSCI leak detector were in logarithmic shielding units (SUs) which were suppose to correspond to the overall shielding effectiveness of a shield room when measured with this technique. In order to make the readings correspond to the theoretical values, 34 dB had to be added to the shielding units.

Figure 4. RF Leak Detector Measurement of Calibrated Apertures

Theory predicts that the shielding effectiveness of a 2 inch diameter hole should be 60 dB and should be inversely proportional to the third power of the aperture diameter. The measurements were consistent with this theory and with each other (after the LFSCI shielding units were normalized).

The maximum shielding effectiveness that could be measured with these instruments was 80 to 90 dB. Within the range of valid measurements, the shielding effectiveness was inversely proportional to the third power of the aperture diameter, as predicted by theory.

When quantitative measurements were first attempted using the LFSCI leak detector, many inconsistencies were observed. Close attention to detail revealed that the readings were extremely sensitive to the distance of the ferrite loop sensor to the shield. Additional measurements showed that the resonant frequency of the sensor was dependent on the sensor to shield distance. Consequently it could be detuned and gave inconsistent results. Particular attention was paid to the sensor to shield distance in order to insure reasonably consistent results.

Field Evaluation

The usefulness of these leak detectors as aircraft hardness surveillance tools was evaluated by using them to measure the shielding effectiveness of windows and doors in a large commercial aircraft that had been modified so that these apertures were electromagnetically hardened. The windows were screened and conductive gaskets replaced the environmental seals on the doors. The electromagnetic performance of these hardened apertures was also measured using an aperture tester [2].

The UHF leak detector was used for only a few measurements because it was difficult to use on an aircraft. The a.c. power requirement for the transmitter limited its mobility. The short wavelength, 0.65 m, meant that the readings depended on the location of the operator and reflections from the walls of the aircraft. Finally, relatively small apertures resonated at 462 MHz. Such apertures will have poor shielding effectiveness at 462 MHz but be relatively unimportant at EMP frequencies.

The bulk of the field evaluation measurements were made with the LF285 and LFSCI leak detectors. The LFSCI was used both from inside to outside and outside to inside. Most LF285 measurements were made with the loops in the coplanar orientation (MIL-STD-285) and in both the vertical and horizontal directions. All window measurements were made at the center of the window. The door measurements were made at the 9 locations shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Location of Leak Detector Measurement on Aircraft Doors

Figure 6 shows the shielding effectiveness of an aircraft window, with and without a shielding screen, as measured using the LFSCI leak detector. For these measurements, shielding effectiveness was defined as the ratio, in decibels, of the surface magnetic field outside the aircraft to the magnetic field a specified distance inside the aperture. The use of this definition was consistent with other measurements [3] and eliminated any confusion over the meaning of shielding units. In order to obtain the shielding effectiveness, the leak detector reading (in shielding units) measured inside was subtracted from the reading obtained on the outside surface. Also shown on Figure 6 is a line that corresponds to an inverse distance cubed relationship expected for an aperture if it behaves like a magnetic dipole. The shielding effectiveness of the clear window is more or less consistent with this relationship. At 6 inches, shielding effectiveness of the clear window was about 23 dB and shielding effectiveness of the screened window was about 34 dB. The difference is 11 dB. This is somewhat low compared to 17 dB, as measured using the SPEHS technique [3], and 22 dB, as measured using the aperture tester [2].

Figure 6. Shielding Effectiveness of Aircraft Window as Measured Using the LFSCI Leak Detector

Table 1 shows the shielding effectiveness of aircraft windows as measured by the LF285 technique. The attenuation measurements on the passenger windows were less in the horizontal direction than in the vertical direction because there were more gaps between the hardening element (screen or metal blank) and the window frame along the vertical portion of the frame than along the horizontal portion. This is consistent with other measurements [3]. The unhardened door window was circular and the measurements made in the two orientations were the same. The measured shielding effectiveness of the unhardened door window, 27 dB, is consistent with an aperture diameter of 8 inches. This is close to the actual window diameter. The shielding effectiveness of the windows, as measured using the LF285 technique were somewhat higher than those obtained by other techniques. To a large extent this is due to the use of different definitions of shielding effectiveness and different measuring distances.

TABLE 1
ATTENUATION OF WINDOWS AS MEASURED
BY THE LF285 LEAK DETECTOR

	Attenuation (dB)	
	Horizontal	Vertical
Screened Window	30	37
Metal Blank #1	32	40
Metal Blank #2	35	40
Metal Blank #3	35	37
Unhardened Door Window	27	27

The shielding effectiveness of the aft galley and forward galley doors were measured using the LF285 and LFSCI leak detectors. The results are shown in Tables 2 and 3. For these measurements, the LFSCI leak detector was used to measure the magnetic field close to the inside surface of the door. The resulting measurements were inconsistent and showed great variability. This was probably due to the detuning of the receiver mentioned earlier. The horizontal and vertical shielding attenuation measurements, made with the LF285 leak detector, are seen to be complimentary to each other. That is, when the shielding effectiveness measured in the vertical direction is high, the horizontal measurement is generally low and vice versa. This results from the fact that the door apertures are long and narrow. Polarizability theory predicts that the magnetic field coupled through the aperture will be much greater if the current flow is across the wide part of the aperture. The coplanar measurements are generally higher than the measurements made with the loops parallel and opposite to one another.

TABLE 2
ATTENUATION OF FORWARD CARGO DOOR

Location	Attenuation (dB) LF285			LFSCI
	Horizontal	Vertical	Parallel	
1. Aft Bottom	35	29	35	17
2. Aft Mid	37	30	30	7
3. Aft Top	35	30	26	-1
4. Top Mid	48	25	32	-5
5. Forward Top	38	33	27	-5
6. Forward Mid	31	44	30	10
7. Forward Bottom	40	32	28	18
8. Bottom Mid	51	20	31	8
9. Center	44	29	63	

TABLE 3
ATTENUATION OF AFT GALLEY DOOR

Location	Attenuation (dB) LF285			LFSCI
	Horizontal	Vertical	Parallel	
1. Aft Bottom	38	34	29	
2. Aft Mid	25	45	33	14
3. Aft Top	41	37	27	
4. Top Mid	48	27	29	-22
5. Forward Top	38	33	26	
6. Forward Mid	24	40	29	10
7. Forward Bottom	45	35	22	18
8. Bottom Mid	54	25	25	11
9. Center	27	29	54	23

Overall Comments

The meter readings of the LF285 leak detector were very steady. Most of the users remarked that these steady readings instilled confidence. For aircraft hardness surveillance, the 150 kHz operating frequency was a little low, since the aircraft's resonant frequencies are in the 1 to 10 MHz range. The LF285 leak detector required 2 people to make the measurements and an additional person to record them. Communications between the person inside and the person outside was sometimes difficult because the doors had to be closed and the measurement location, an aircraft parking area, was noisy. The measurements were generally consistent with each other and with theory.

The meter readings of the UHF leak detector were variable because of standing waves and possible coupling to the operators. This severely reduced

their credibility. The wavelength, 0.65 m, was probably too short for apertures of the size found in reasonably hardened aircraft. This leak detector was more appropriate for good shielding enclosures such as screen room. The requirement for a.c. power for the transmitter limited the mobility of the instrument and therefore its usefulness. As with the LF285 leak detector, two people were required for most aircraft measurements plus an additional person to record the results.

The greatest disadvantage of the LFSCI leak detector was that the receiving unit detuned when the sensor was close to a metallic surface. This problem could be solved with an appropriated design of the sensor and detector circuitry. The use of shielding units (SU's) was confusing. During the field evaluation, this problem was solved by using the detector to measure the ratio of the magnetic fields a prescribed distance outside and inside the aircraft. Only one operator was required plus a person to record the data. The readings were reasonably stable. However, the frequency, 95 kHz may be somewhat low for credible aircraft hardness surveillance measurements.

Conclusions

The electromagnetic characterization of three commercial RF leak detectors showed that the low frequency measurements were more stable than the high frequency measurements, but the measurement frequency was somewhat low for credible aircraft hardness surveillance since it was about a decade below the fundamental resonance of typical aircraft. The UHF measurements were quite variable and did not inspire confidence, especially for evaluating aperture sizes found on aircraft. Skin current excitation was more convenient than localized field excitation because it was simpler (the excitation source did not have to be moved for different measurement locations) and it was easier to excite and find all the "EM hot spots." The EM leak detector measurements were consistent with theory, thereby demonstrating that they could be used in a quantitative manner. Finally, the battery operated instruments were much more useful and convenient than the A.C. operated instruments.

References

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